

Family Educational Role in Facing Gender-Based Violence in Early Childhood: Implications for Primary Education

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Table 1: The distribution of the study sample according to its variables

Variables	Levels	Fathers		Mothers	
		Repetition	Percentage	Repetition	Percentage
Academic Qualification	Diploma and less	96	28.24%	86	25.29%
	Bachelor	193	56.76%	213	62.65%
	Postgraduate Studies	51	15.00%	41	12.06%
Type of the Work of Parents	Public Sector	91	26.76%	61	17.94%
	Private Sector	181	53.24%	96	28.24%
	Self-Employment	68	20.00%	==	==
	Unemployed or a Housewife	==	==	183	53.82%
Number of Children in the Family	1-2 Children	193		56.76%	
	3-4 Children	97		28.53%	
	5 Children & More	50		14.71%	
Total		340	100.00%	340	100.00%